

Supplemental Appendix for Signaling Restraint: International Engagement and Rebel Groups' Commitment to International Law

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Contents

1	Summary Statistics	2
2	Note on Sample Construction	6
3	Additional Substantive Effects	10
4	Robustness Checks	13
4.1	Potential Confounding Factors and Alternative Measure of Democracy	13
4.2	Logit Regression of Rebel Commitment without Peace Agreement	15
4.3	Cross-Sectional Analysis	17
4.4	Interaction Effects	19
4.5	Peace Agreement Effects & Potential Endogeneity	24
4.5.1	Comparison of rebel commitment before and after peace agreement . .	24
4.5.2	Civil Society Participation in Peace Negotiations	27
5	Model Performance	30
6	Text Analysis	31
6.1	Word clouds	31
6.2	Topic Models	33
6.3	Examples of Contents and Contexts	35

1 Summary Statistics

The following table presents summary statistics of the main variables used in the analysis in the paper.

Table A1-1: Summary Statistics of Main Variables

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Median	Maximum
Commitment	0.073	0.260	0	0	1
Non-military Transnational Support	0.373	0.484	0	0	1
Near Peace Talks	0.123	0.329	0	0	1
Central Control Strength	1.924	0.745	0	2	3
Military Strength	0.613	0.658	0	1	4
Territorial Control	0.410	0.492	0	0	1
Military Transnational Support	0.279	0.448	0	0	1
Secessionist	0.364	0.481	0	0	1
Age of Rebel Group	8.209	8.260	1	5	47
Extraterritorial Bases	0.662	0.473	0	1	1
Support by Foreign Government	1.162	0.951	0	2	2
Political Wings	0.539	0.727	0	0	2
Number of Rebel Groups	1.957	2.229	0	1	10
Democracy	0.325	0.469	0	0	1
Time (year counter)	19.105	9.923	1	19	37
<i>N</i> = 1944					

Table A1-2: Cross tabulation of *Rebel Commitment* and *Non-military Transnational Support*

	No transnational support	Yes transnational support	Total
No commit	201	77	278
Yes commit	32	28	60
Total	233	107	338
Percentage of Commitment	14%	27%	

Note to Table A1-2. The table presents the number of rebel groups for each category in the dimension of rebel commitment and transnational support for rebels. The cross-tabulation shows that rebels with transnational non-military support are more likely to make soft international law commitments (27% versus 14%). Among the rebel groups without transnational support, only 14% (32 out of 201 groups) commit to international law. By contrast, among the rebel groups with transnational support, 27% (28 out of 207 groups) commit to international law.

Table A1-3: Cross tabulation of *Rebel Commitment* and *Central Control Strength*

	No central control	Weak central control	Moderate central control	Strong central control	Total
No commit	18	33	167	51	269
Yes commit	0	11	29	23	63
Total	18	44	196	74	332
Percentage of Commitment	0%	25%	15%	31%	

Note to Table A1-3. The table reports the number of rebel groups in each category with respect to their command-and-control strength and their international law commitment behavior. Note that a larger share of groups with strong central control commit to international law, relative to all other categories. For example, no rebel group with zero central control ever commits to international law, in contrast to 31% groups committing to international law when they have strong central command. We also note a somewhat non-linear trend between control strength and commitment. The share of committers is higher for groups with weak central control (25%) relative to their counterparts with moderate central control (15%). But with few groups in the category of weak central control, we do not want to infer too much out of the trend.

Table A1-4: Cross tabulation of *Rebel Commitment* and *Near Peace Talks*

	Not near peace talks	Yes, near peace talks	Total
No commit	1627	175	1802
Yes commit	77	65	142
Total	1704	240	1944
Percentage of Commitment	5%	27%	

Note to Table A1-4. Each observation is a rebel group-year (not the number of rebel groups). Among the rebel-group years near peace talks, rebel commitment to international law is much more frequently occurring (27%, 65 rebel group-year observations out of 175 rebel group-year observations). Rebel groups commit to international law only 5% of the time (77 observations out of 1,627) without proximity to peace talks.

2 Note on Sample Construction

We collected 404 documents between 1974 and 2010 from *Theirwords* database and other secondary sources. Our analysis focuses on relatively militarily capable groups and main sample of rebel groups comes from the NSA dataset which includes only rebel groups involved in a conflict generating at least 25 battle deaths in a given year. This means that rebel groups that are not within the NSA data and the associated documents drop from our main dataset in the merging process. This cuts the number of documents from 404 to 212, with the effect of 192 documents remaining outside of the scope of our analysis. We are mindful of missing these documents and discuss in greater detail a related robustness checks here in the online appendix.

In terms of the number of rebel groups, this translates into 64 out of 364 rebel groups (about 18%) in our sample making these 212 commitment documents. Within those 64 groups, 30 made multiple commitments in a year, making them multiple-time committers, while the remaining 34 groups as one-time committers. Among those 212 documents, 18 out of 212 documents were jointly signed by multiple rebel groups, so they appear in our dataset as multiple counts. 14% of the commitments in our dataset are the documents made with the Geneva Call. There is a large difference between the Geneva Call's source data (*Theirwords* database) and Geneva Call related commitments. The resulting dependent variable in the dataset, rebel commitment, is a dichotomous indicator coded as 1 (i.e., "committed") for 142 out of 1944 observations for each rebel group - year. We summarize the information below as a table as well as a figure.

Table A2-1: Summary of Rebel Commitment - *In terms of the number of documents, number of rebel groups, and number of observations*

Number of total commitment documents in Theirwords database	Number of commitment documents made into our dataset	Number of rebel groups that committed to international law	Number of observation (rebel group - year) coded as "committed"
404	212	64	142

Figure A2-1: Venn Diagram of Rebel Commitment Documents.

As explained above, to construct our cross-sectional time series dataset for the main analyses, we matched rebel groups in *Theirwords* archive to rebel groups in the NSA dataset. Because the NSA dataset only contains rebel groups that have generated at least 25 battle deaths in a given year, some groups are mismatched or lost in the merging process. The reasons for mismatch are twofold; one is the mismatch in rebel groups, and the other is the mismatch in year of activity. The former is the case where a rebel group made commitments identified by Geneva Call but never appears in the NSA dataset. We call this a “group-mismatch” problem. The other type of mismatch arises from discrepancies between the years when a rebel group engaged in violent conflicts and the years when it committed to international law. We call this a “year-mismatch” problem.

As our research attempts to explain why *violent* rebel groups make commitments to international law and the NSA dataset has reasonable criteria for classifying violent rebel organizations), we do not expect that the group-mismatch problem undermines the validity of our empirical results. The fact that a rebel group fails to be merged to the NSA dataset means that they never engaged in any violent conflicts generating at least 25 annual fatalities. If we were to include all imaginable weak and obscure groups into the sample, we surmise that the coefficients for our key covariates would increase. It is because those obscure groups would have low values of all the key independent variables and limited opportunity to commit, as we argue in the paper.¹

Unlike the group-mismatch problem, however, year-mismatch problem may cause a problem for our inference. More specifically, some commitments made by 52 out of 364 rebel groups in the NSA dataset are not accounted for in our main analyses because these 52 groups did not engage in violent conflicts in the years when they committed to international law.² Thus, omitting the commitments made by these 52 groups due to the discrepancies in temporal coverage may bias our estimates. To address this concern, we added the missing commitment year observations to our main dataset and re-estimated the main models.³ As seen in Table A2-2 below, our main empirical results hold as we account for the additional commitments made in the years when rebel groups did not engage in violent conflicts.

¹These are the rebel groups that are featured in the *Theirwords* database but not in the NSA dataset. List on file with the authors.

²Once we account for these omitted commitments, the number of rebel groups with at least one commitment rises to 94.

³To this end, we add not only year-mismatch observations (94 observations) but also extra observations up to 2 years ahead, at maximum, of the year-mismatch observation (106 observations). In the original NSA data, for instance, the last observation for Patriotic Union of Kurdistan (PUK) in Iraq is year of 1996, though this rebel group made a unilateral declaration of upholding to a total ban on anti-personnel mines in 2000 and 2002. Thus, we append not just 2 observations for “year mismatch” cases (PUK-2000 and PUK-2002) but also 3 extra observations (PUK-1998, PUK-1999, and PUK-2001). Although setting 2 years is arbitrary, the results do not greatly change when we add only year-mismatch observations (94 observations).

Table A2-2: Logit Analysis of Rebel Commitment to International law (including “year-mismatch” observations)

	Model 1	Model 2
	Pooled logit	Random Effects logit
Non-military Transnational Support	1.018*** (0.279)	1.195*** (0.313)
Near Peace Talks	1.745*** (0.231)	1.806*** (0.223)
Central Control Strength	0.456*** (0.139)	0.642*** (0.193)
Military Strength	0.196 (0.173)	0.287 (0.187)
Territorial Control	0.643*** (0.218)	0.770*** (0.272)
Military Transnational Support	-0.452 (0.308)	-0.568* (0.333)
Secessionist	-0.158 (0.262)	-0.403 (0.307)
Age of Rebel Group	0.083*** (0.018)	0.093*** (0.018)
Extraterritorial Bases	0.031 (0.276)	-0.032 (0.299)
Support by Foreign Government (Base = No support)		
Non-military	-0.780* (0.430)	-0.963* (0.546)
Military	-0.072 (0.254)	-0.097 (0.282)
Political Wings (Base = No wings)		
Unauthorized Wings	-0.202 (0.325)	-0.169 (0.325)
Legal Wings	0.046 (0.275)	0.011 (0.357)
Number of Rebel Groups	-0.018 (0.047)	-0.011 (0.057)
Democracy	-0.111 (0.274)	-0.151 (0.280)
Time (1 = Year of 1974)	0.066*** (0.013)	0.073*** (0.015)
Time Since Last Commitment (t)	-0.093 (0.072)	0.008 (0.082)
t^2	0.001 (0.007)	-0.005 (0.008)
t^3	-0.000 (0.000)	0.000 (0.000)
Constant	-5.811*** (0.603)	-6.960*** (0.799)
Variance (Rebel Groups)		0.660** (0.267)
Observations	1876	1876
AIC	999.07	985.17

Clustered standard errors (by rebel groups) in parentheses

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

3 Additional Substantive Effects

Table A3-1: Difference in Predicted Probability of Commitment between Rebel Groups with and without Non-military Transnational Support

	Mean	Confidence Interval (95%)
Pr(Commitment Transnational support) - Pr(Commitment Non-transnational support)	0.056	[.020, .096]

Table A3-2: Difference in Predicted Probability of Commitment between Rebel Groups away from Peace Talks vs. Near Peace Talks

	Mean	Confidence Interval (95%)
Pr(Commitment Near peace talks) - Pr(Commitment Away peace talks)	0.123	[.083, .173]

Figure A3-1: Difference in Predicted Probabilities of Rebel Commitment: Two Scenarios of Central Command Strengths, Low and Moderate.

Note to Figure A3-1. The top panel presents changes in predicted probability of commitment as rebel groups' central command strength shifts from "Low" to each level of strength, whereas bottom panel presents those as the central command strength shifts from "Moderate" to each level of strength. Using the estimates from Model 2 in Table 1 in the paper, we calculated the differences in predicted probabilities of rebel commitment to international law as rebel groups' central control strength changes, holding the other covariates at the observed values for each observation in the sample. Black circles are point estimates and black bars represent 95% confidence intervals of those point estimates. Both panels show that rebel groups with strong central command and control structures are more likely to make international law commitments.

Figure A3-2: Predicted Probabilities of Rebel Commitment According to *Age of Rebel Group*.

Note to Figure A3-2. This Figure presents the predicted probabilities of rebel commitment to international law (vertical axis) across the age of the rebel group (horizontal axis). Using the estimates from Model 2 in Table 1, we calculated the predicted probabilities of rebel commitment to international law, holding covariates at the observed values for each observation in the sample. Blue lines are point estimates and shaded region represents 95% confidence intervals of those point estimates. Additionally, the lightly shaded histogram describes the distribution of rebel age in our sample.

4 Robustness Checks

4.1 Potential Confounding Factors and Alternative Measure of Democracy

We examined the robustness of our findings to alternative model specifications by controlling for two other variables that might alter the likelihood of rebel commitment to international law and are correlated with our key explanatory variables.

First, we accounted for *Human Rights* practices for each country. The level of human rights in a host country might determine the extent to which rebel groups are pressured to uphold values related to human rights, or use commitments to distinguish themselves from the government. We measured Human Rights using the latent measure developed by Fariss (2014).

Then we report the results of using a different measure of regime types of the national governments, polity2 scores from Polity IV project, instead of the measure derived from GWF typology. We also report models with the Cold War and Jihadist variables included in separate models, as we combine them in Model 3 of the manuscript.

All models in Table A4-1 are estimated using the random effects logit estimator. Including these variables does not affect our main results. Although the coefficients on main predictors change somewhat across the models, our key inferences hold when controlling for each confounding factor we introduced above. The likelihood of rebel groups' expressing a commitment to international law is not correlated with the Cold War dummy (Model 2), suggesting weak evidence of reciprocal commitment or the Cold War influence.

While Human rights scores (Model 1) and Jihadist ideology (Model 3) are negatively associated with the likelihood of rebel groups' commitment to international law, accounting for these factors do not greatly change our findings. The results of Model 4 show that the likelihood of rebel commitment has no clear association with the regime type of the national governments and that our main results are consistent across different measures of political regimes.

Table A4-1: Robustness Check I: Potential Confounding Factors & Alternative Measure of Democracy)

	Model 1 Human Rights Score	Model 2 Polity 2
Non-military Transnational Support	1.010*** (0.349)	1.029*** (0.328)
Near Peace Talks	1.817*** (0.265)	1.756*** (0.261)
Central Control Strength	0.719*** (0.227)	0.710*** (0.216)
Military Strength	0.445** (0.219)	0.359* (0.214)
Territorial Control	0.483 (0.328)	0.805*** (0.296)
Military Transnational Support	-0.287 (0.369)	-0.311 (0.353)
Secessionist	-0.408 (0.391)	-0.526 (0.363)
Age of Rebel Group	0.073*** (0.018)	0.077*** (0.017)
Extraterritorial Bases	0.499 (0.366)	0.374 (0.360)
Support by Foreign Government		
Non-military	-1.377* (0.715)	-1.277*** (0.616)
Military	-0.092 (0.315)	0.220 (0.309)
Political Wings		
Unauthorized Wings	-0.248 (0.423)	-0.320 (0.398)
Legal Wings	0.101 (0.399)	0.127 (0.383)
Number of Rebel Groups	-0.192* (0.103)	-0.109 (0.089)
Democracy (GWF)	0.303 (0.359)	
Time (1 = Year of 1974)	0.076*** (0.017)	0.066*** (0.016)
Time Since Last Commitment (t)	-0.059 (0.081)	-0.106 (0.079)
t^2	-0.003 (0.006)	-0.001 (0.006)
t^3	0.000 (0.000)	0.000 (0.000)
Human Rights Scores	-0.501* (0.266)	
Democracy (Polity2)		0.374 (0.346)
Constant	-8.213*** (1.070)	-7.360*** (0.923)
Variance (Rebel Group)	0.396 (0.243)	0.382 (0.248)
Observations	1713	1647
AIC	656.029	671.552
Standard errors in parentheses *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$		

4.2 Logit Regression of Rebel Commitment without Peace Agreement

Because the rebel commitment documents include peace agreements, our main results might have an endogeneity problem if there are many cases in which rebel groups made only peace agreements without other commitments. Among the total 142 instances of commitment, only 30 instances (21%) are the cases where peace agreements are the only commitment that rebel groups made in a given year. To examine whether our main findings, particularly the positive coefficients on *Near Peace Talk*, are the artifact of including those 30 cases in the sample, we estimated the main models with a new dependent variable that does not include peace agreements. That is, the new dependent variable was coded as 1 if a rebel group made any international law commitment except for peace agreement in a given year and 0 otherwise. We estimate the same two model specifications reported in the paper with this alternative dependent variable and report the results in Table A4-2 below.

The results show that our key findings still hold even when we do not count peace agreements as international law commitment. In particular, the positive and statistically significant coefficient on *Near Peace Talk* implies that rebel groups' incentives to commit to international law rise with greater proximity to peace negotiations, even without accounting for commitments in the peace agreements themselves.

Table A4-2: Robustness Check II: Logit Regression of Rebel Commitment without Peace Agreement

	Model 1 Pooled logit	Model 2 Random Effects logit
Non-military Transnational Support	1.237*** (0.365)	1.278*** (0.355)
Near Peace Talks	1.008*** (0.303)	1.019*** (0.286)
Central Control Strength	0.396** (0.161)	0.496** (0.228)
Military Strength	0.205 (0.211)	0.234 (0.234)
Territorial Control	0.759*** (0.251)	0.860*** (0.319)
Military Transnational Support	-0.604 (0.390)	-0.550 (0.375)
Secessionist	-0.424 (0.355)	-0.568 (0.402)
Age of Rebel Group	0.076*** (0.017)	0.074*** (0.018)
Extraterritorial Bases	0.855* (0.479)	0.848** (0.398)
Support by Foreign Government (Base = No support)		
Non-military	-1.167** (0.569)	-1.330* (0.776)
Military	-0.179 (0.327)	-0.222 (0.325)
Political Wings (Base = No wings)		
Unauthorized Wings	0.050 (0.498)	0.009 (0.427)
Legal Wings	0.114 (0.327)	0.129 (0.424)
Number of Rebel Groups	-0.191 (0.117)	-0.183* (0.109)
Democracy	0.320 (0.354)	0.296 (0.355)
Time (1 = Year of 1974)	0.073*** (0.018)	0.076*** (0.018)
Time Since Last Commitment (t)	-0.196*** (0.074)	-0.153* (0.087)
t^2	0.004 (0.007)	0.002 (0.007)
t^3	-0.000 (0.000)	-0.000 (0.000)
Constant	-6.450*** (0.949)	-6.981*** (1.072)
Variance (Rebel group)		0.275 (0.243)
Observations	1713	1713
AIC	576.82	576.72

Clustered standard errors (by rebel groups) in parentheses

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

4.3 Cross-Sectional Analysis

Because most of our rebel-group level explanatory variables are time-invariant, cross-sectional analysis of rebel commitment should yield similar results. For the cross-sectional analysis in which the unit of analysis is a rebel group, we aggregated the dependent variable in two ways. On the one hand, we coded the dependent variable as 1 if the rebel group has ever committed to international law and 0 otherwise. Columns 1 and 3 show the results of logit regression of this binary dependent variable. We also counted the number of commitments that each rebel group made. The resulting count variable has several distinct values and is highly skewed,⁴ so we used a negative binomial estimator. We present the results in columns 2 and 4 of the table below (Table A4-3).

We also aggregated the explanatory variables in two ways. For the dichotomous variables, we coded them as 1 if the rebel group has ever had the given characteristic and 0 otherwise. If a rebel group received non-military support from transnational organizations at least once, for instance, we coded the variable *Transnational Support* as 1 for this rebel group. For the variables with ordinal scales or multiple nominal categories such as the composite index of rebels' military strength (*Military Strength*) and the categorical variable of rebel groups' political wings (*Political Wings*), we took the average over time and then rounded it to the nearest integer.⁵ To examine the effect of peace talks in cross-sectional analysis, we employed two types of variables. The first type is a binary indicator of peace talks (*Peace Talks*), coded as 1 if the rebel group has ever had peace negotiations in our sample and 0 otherwise. The second type captures the total number of peace negotiations that the rebel group had in our sample (*Number of Peace Talks*). For the case of UNITA in Angola that made four peace agreements between 1975 and 2002, for example, the value of first cross-sectional measure, *Peace Talks*, is one whereas the value of second measure, *Number of Peace Talks*, is four. We used the dichotomous variable in Models 1 and 2 and employed the other variable capturing cumulative number of peace talks in Models 3 and 4.

The results reported in the table are analogous to the panel data analyses in the manuscript. The results of cross-sectional logit regression models (Models 1 and 3) show that the likelihood of rebel commitment is greater for those rebel groups with non-military support from transnational organizations, strong central control, and the experience of peace negotiations. Similarly, the positive coefficients estimated from negative binomial models (Models 2 and 4) tell us that the number of international law commitments by a rebel group increases as they receive non-military aids from transnational sponsors, have strong central control, and participate in more peace talks.⁶

⁴About 82 percent of the rebel groups in the NSA data never made any commitment.

⁵Because most variables of rebel groups' characteristics in the NSA dataset are indeed invariant over time, the results of cross-sectional analysis do not greatly change with the ways of collapsing the explanatory variables.

⁶All of these estimated coefficients are statistically significant at least at the 90% level, except for the coefficient on *Transnational Support* in model 3, whose p -value is slightly greater than 0.1 ($p = 0.107$).

Table A4-3: Robustness Check II: Logit Regression of Rebel Commitment without Peace Agreement

	Model 1 DV: Dummy for Commitment	Model 2 DV: Number of Commitment	Model 3 DV: Dummy for Commitment	Model 4 DV: Number of Commitment
Non-military Transnational Support	1.159* (0.617)	1.110*** (0.329)	1.056 (0.655)	1.179*** (0.345)
Peace Talks	2.571*** (0.488)	2.115*** (0.327)		
Number of Peace Talks			0.898*** (0.202)	0.441*** (0.081)
Central Control Strength	1.440*** (0.409)	0.841*** (0.227)	1.547*** (0.406)	1.173*** (0.251)
Military Strength	0.381 (0.312)	0.371* (0.203)	0.362 (0.307)	0.424** (0.209)
Territorial Control	0.973* (0.532)	0.845*** (0.289)	0.755 (0.523)	0.900*** (0.303)
Military Transnational Support	-0.290 (0.696)	-0.589 (0.375)	-0.266 (0.697)	-0.528 (0.375)
Secessionist	-0.811 (0.650)	-0.217 (0.403)	-0.700 (0.624)	-0.439 (0.379)
Age of Rebel Groups	0.204*** (0.050)	0.174*** (0.027)	0.189*** (0.048)	0.160*** (0.028)
Extraterritorial Bases	0.370 (0.600)	0.738* (0.395)	0.181 (0.614)	0.949** (0.400)
Support by Foreign Government (Base = No support)				
Non-military	-1.164 (0.956)	-1.202** (0.596)	-1.090 (1.014)	-1.115* (0.626)
Military	0.551 (0.540)	0.097 (0.297)	0.825** (0.542)	0.108 (0.311)
Political Wings (Base = No wings)				
Unauthorized Wings	-1.012 (0.646)	-0.368 (0.408)	-0.982 (0.667)	-0.675 (0.437)
Legal Wings	-0.628 (0.662)	0.552 (0.396)	-0.813 (0.674)	0.168 (0.406)
Number of Rebel Groups	-0.264 (0.174)	-0.353*** (0.126)	-0.227 (0.161)	-0.231* (0.118)
Democracy	0.356 (0.563)	0.138 (0.329)	0.385 (0.547)	0.580* (0.326)
Time (1 = Year of 1974)	0.095*** (0.030)	0.103*** (0.020)	0.097*** (0.029)	0.103*** (0.021)
Constant	-9.123*** (1.685)	-7.564*** (1.032)	-8.977*** (1.633)	-8.192*** (1.115)
Dispersion Parameter (α)		0.809*** (0.274)		1.012*** (0.290)
Observations	290	290	290	290
AIC	179.260	399.922	180.959	405.600

Clustered standard errors (by rebel groups) in parentheses

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

4.4 Interaction Effects

Our theoretical mechanism suggests potential interactions among our independent variables. Specifically, the effect of rebel capacity can be augmented by the presence of transnational actors. Likewise, the effect of peace agreements timing may be increased by the presence of transnational support. We test these mechanisms in interaction models. Below, we report the results in a series of tables and figures. Table A4-4, Figure A4-1, and Figure A4-2 pertain to the interaction effect between *Transnational Support* and *Central Control Strength*. Table A4-5 pertains to the interaction effect between *Transnational Support* and *Near Peace Talks*.

Table A4-4 demonstrates that the interaction effect between transnational support and rebel command and control is statistically significant and positive. Transnational support reinforces the effect of rebel command and control, and vice-versa. This is consistent with our argument that international actors can more easily identify rebel interlocutors when the group has clear central command and control, and that command gives rebels capacity to take advantage of these interactions.

Figure A4-1 shows how the effect of transnational support changes across the level of central control strengths. When the rebel groups have “no” or “low” central control capacity, the effect of transnational support is not statistically significant at 95% level. This means that rebel groups with transnational support are not more likely to commit to international laws than those without it as they lack central control structures. However, if they have viable central command structures, then the transnational support does make a difference: rebel groups with transnational support are more likely to commit to international laws than those without it. And this difference increases as the level of central control strength increases.

Table A4-5 reports a null finding about the interaction effect between *Transnational Support* and *Near Peace Talks*. Although we argued that transnational support could facilitate rebel commitment near peace time, our estimates do not reflect this. The might suggest there is weak link between the operation of peace talks timing and transnational support. This also hints at the differences in the kinds of international actors in terms of involvement during civil wars and during peace talks. Peace talks usually involve mediators and other countries with interests in that particular civil conflict. These might be different from diaspora, ethnic kin, or humanitarian actor involvement during the course of the conflict.

Figure A4-2 shows how transnational support modifies the effect of peace talks. When a rebel group has no transnational support, proximity to peace talks increases the probability of international law commitment by 11 percentage points. If transnational support is present, proximity to peace talks increases the probability of commitment by 14 percentage points. The 95% confidence intervals for these estimates overlap substantially, however. As a result, the two predicted probabilities are statistically indistinguishable from one another. There is little evidence of an interaction between transnational support and proximity to peace talks.

Table A4-4: Robustness Check IV: Interaction Effects (*Transnational Support* x *Central Control Strength*)

	Model 1 Pooled logit	Model 2 Random Effects logit
Non-military Transnational Support	-0.296 (0.751)	-0.439 (0.901)
Central Control Strength	0.253 (0.204)	0.366 (0.276)
Non-military Transnational Support x Central Control Strength	0.687** (0.318)	0.768 (0.421)
Near Peace Talks	1.739*** (0.287)	1.823*** (0.265)
Military Strength	0.368* (0.193)	0.427 (0.219)
Territorial Control	0.601** (0.256)	0.716** (0.305)
Military Transnational Support	-0.534 (0.432)	-0.440 (0.379)
Secessionist	-0.428 (0.360)	-0.599 (0.390)
Age of Rebel Group	0.075*** (0.015)	0.073*** (0.018)
Extraterritorial Bases	0.489 (0.356)	0.476 (0.368)
Support by Foreign Government		
Non-military	-1.315** (0.549)	-1.457** (0.724)
Military	0.028 (0.329)	-0.045 (0.318)
Political Wings		
Unauthorized Wings	-0.347 (0.440)	-0.410 (0.425)
Legal Wings	0.183 (0.325)	0.148 (0.401)
Number of Rebel Groups	-0.127 (0.104)	-0.116 (0.096)
Democracy	0.096 (0.370)	0.039 (0.351)
Time (1 = Year of 1974)	0.073*** (0.017)	0.079*** (0.017)
Time Since Last Commitment (t)	-0.107 (0.071)	-0.042 (0.081)
t^2	-0.001 (0.006)	-0.004 (0.006)
t^3	0.000 (0.000)	0.000 (0.000)
Constant	-6.059*** (0.908)	-6.792*** (1.045)
Variance (Rebel Group)		0.426* (0.253)
Observations	1713	1713
AIC	660.52	656.28

Clustered standard errors (by rebel groups) in parentheses

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Figure A4-1: First-Difference in Predicted Probabilities of Rebel Commitment across Central Control Strength.

Note to Figure A4-1: This Figure presents the difference in predicted probability of rebel commitment between rebel groups with transnational support and those without it (vertical axis) at each level of central control strength (horizontal axis). Using the estimates from Model 2 in Table A4-4, we calculated the predicted probabilities of rebel commitment to international law, holding covariates at the observed values for each observation in the sample, and then computed the difference in those probabilities. Black circles are point estimates and black bars represent 95% confidence intervals of those point estimates. The shaded histogram plots the number of observations for each category of central control strength.

Table A4-5: Robustness Check V: Interaction Effects (*Transnational Support* x *Near Peace Talks*)

	Model 1 Pooled logit	Model 2 Random Effects logit
Non-military Transnational Support	1.300*** (0.454)	1.292*** (0.409)
Near Peace Talks	1.990*** (0.382)	2.043*** (0.346)
Non-military Transnational Support x Near Peace Talks	-0.545 (0.541)	-0.486 (0.497)
Central Control Strength	0.537*** (0.154)	0.692*** (0.227)
Military Strength	0.355 * (0.200)	0.420* (0.219)
Territorial Control	0.656*** (0.252)	0.750** (0.306)
Military Transnational Support	-0.424 (0.412)	-0.330 (0.370)
Secessionist	-0.424 (0.342)	-0.579 (0.393)
Age of Rebel Group	0.078*** (0.015)	0.075*** (0.018)
Extraterritorial Bases	0.536 (0.372)	0.502 (0.370)
Support by Foreign Government		
Non-military	-1.242 ** (0.580)	-1.379* (0.717)
Military	-0.029 (0.319)	-0.060 (0.319)
Political Wings		
Unauthorized Wings	-0.309 (0.472)	-0.363 (0.422)
Legal Wings	0.117 (0.332)	0.098 (0.405)
Number of Rebel Groups	-0.127 (0.102)	-0.115 (0.096)
Democracy	0.173 (0.349)	0.110 (0.349)
Time (1 = Year of 1974)	0.067*** (0.017)	0.074*** (0.017)
Time Since Last Commitment (<i>t</i>)	-0.122* (0.074)	-0.051 (0.081)
<i>t</i> ²	-0.000 (0.006)	-0.004 (0.006)
<i>t</i> ³	0.000 (0.000)	0.000 (0.000)
Constant	-6.679*** (0.934)	-7.533*** (1.039)
Variance (Rebel Groups)		0.445* (0.263)
Observations	1713	1713
AIC	663.01	658.72

Clustered standard errors (by rebel groups) in parentheses

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Figure A4-2: First-Difference in Predicted Probabilities of Rebel Commitment by Near Peace Talks: Comparing with and without *Transnational Support*.

Note to Figure A4-2: This Figure presents the difference in predicted probability of rebel commitment between rebel groups based on proximity to peace talks (vertical axis) at each category of transnational support (horizontal axis). Using the estimates from Model 2 in Table A4-5, we calculated the predicted probabilities of rebel commitment to international law, holding covariates at the observed values for each observation in the sample, and then computed the difference in those probabilities. Black circles are point estimates and black bars represent 95% confidence intervals of those point estimates. The shaded histogram plots the number of observations for each category of transnational support.

4.5 Peace Agreement Effects & Potential Endogeneity

Since the coding of “Near Peace Talks” was coded retrospectively (as the year before and the year of peace talks), we want to investigate how prevalent are cases where as a stipulation for the peace deal the rebel group was required to make some sort of legal commitment. If this were the case, it would be less negotiations acting as a signal of willingness to commitment, but rather commitment as a consequence of negotiations. In order to figure out what produced rebel commitment during peace talks, we conducted further analyses in two ways: 1) by looking at the breakdown of commitments before and after peace agreements, and 2) by examining the cases where civil society was involved and potentially pushed rebel groups to international law commitments.

4.5.1 Comparison of rebel commitment before and after peace agreement

The fact that about 60% (64 out of 110) of commitments made near peace talks are not peace-agreements implies that rebels do have an incentive to express commitment, which is differentiated from the pressure by other warring parties or signatories of peace treaties. We further broke down the rebel commitments into each stage of peace talk: pre, during and post. If it is the case commitments occur predominantly before peace talks, we can have some confidence that it was not the peace agreements that were driving the commitment, but the expectation of peace agreements that produced commitments.

Figure A4-3 presents the distribution of rebel commitments for three stages of peace talks: pre, during and post. The top panel shows one-year time window before and after peace talks (i.e. $t-1$ & $t+1$), while the bottom panel shows two-year time window before and after peace talks (i.e. $t-2$ & $t+2$). Note that the number of commitments is higher for the pre-agreement period, compared to the post-agreement period. This observation is consistent with our interpretation that rebel groups are more likely to utilize rebel commitment as a signal for moderation leading up to the peace talks.

Figure A4-3: Rebel Commitment & the Stage of Peace Talks.

Estimating the likelihood of rebel commitment after peace agreement can be another way to examine whether rebel commitment during peace negotiation periods is attributed to stipulation for peace agreements rather than rebel groups' strategic signaling motivation. It might be reasonable to assume that if warring parties during peace negotiations urge each other to make additional commitments to international law, they will also be forced to make similar commitments after the peace agreements are successfully made. As a number of cases with comprehensive peace agreements containing clauses on requirements and detailed procedures of implementing human rights provisions, warring parties keep monitoring each other and urging their opponents to abide by humanitarian norms after signing the peace agreements. This implies that the atmosphere to put pressures on warring parties to make commitments to international law may persist in post-agreement periods. Thus, if rebel groups are usually forced to make commitments to international law in addition to peace agreements during peace negotiation periods, we may expect that rebel commitments are also more likely in post-agreement periods.

To test this expectation, we generate four dichotomous variables indicating pre or post periods of peace agreements with different time windows and estimate the relationship between rebel commitment and each of the dichotomous variables. Table A4-6 reports the results. Models 1 and 2 include the binary variables indicating the previous years of peace agreement, whereas Models 3 and 4 include those for the next years of peace agreement. We intentionally exclude the observations for the year of peace agreements (t) from the estimation.

According to the results, rebel groups are more likely to commit to international law for the previous years of peace agreements. The coefficients on the binary variables for pre-agreement periods are consistently positive and statistically significant at the 90% level. For the indicators of post-agreement periods, however, the estimated coefficients are negative and statistically insignificant, meaning that rebel groups are unlikely to make more commitments after signing onto the peace agreements. This result implies that the cases in which commitments to international law are required for reaching final agreements in peace negotiations may not be prevalent. Of course, warring parties are often concerned about the risk of their opponents' violating promises of human rights and these concerns might keep them from reaching final agreements. In this case, however, they may pursue to develop more powerful tools to constrain their opponents than requiring verbal commitments to international law as a stipulation. Designing more comprehensive agreements with detailed procedures for monitoring and specific provisions for punishments for violations can be such a typically preferred way to address commitment problems.

Table A4-6: Rebel Commitment for Pre/Post-agreement

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Pre-agreement ($t - 1$)	0.750*			
	(0.435)			
Pre-agreement ($t - 1$ & $t - 2$)		0.654*		
		(0.378)		
Post-agreement ($t + 1$)			-0.720	
			(0.613)	
Post-agreement ($t + 1$ & $t + 2$)				-0.528
				(0.472)
Non-military Transnational Support	1.359***	1.357***	1.374***	1.374***
	(0.447)	(0.444)	(0.443)	(0.445)
Central Control Strength	0.791***	0.782***	0.814***	0.821***
	(0.296)	(0.295)	(0.296)	(0.297)
Military Strength	0.035	0.022	0.123	0.131
	(0.307)	(0.309)	(0.303)	(0.304)
Territorial Control	1.221***	1.199***	1.279***	1.287***
	(0.403)	(0.401)	(0.405)	(0.406)
Military Transnational Support	-0.511	-0.493	-0.598	-0.617
	(0.471)	(0.468)	(0.473)	(0.476)
Secessionist	-0.892*	-0.870*	-1.018***	-1.020***
	(0.465)	(0.464)	(0.463)	(0.465)
Age of Rebel Group	0.062***	0.064***	0.058***	0.058***
	(0.021)	(0.021)	(0.021)	(0.021)
Extraterritorial Bases	0.790*	0.784*	0.917**	0.930**
	(0.470)	(0.466)	(0.467)	(0.470)
Support by Foreign Government				
Non-military	-1.284	-1.296	-1.258	-1.253
	(0.899)	(0.891)	(0.895)	(0.900)
Military	-0.241	-0.246	-0.237	-0.250
	(0.403)	(0.400)	(0.401)	(0.403)
Political Wings				
Unauthorized Wings	-0.429	-0.422	-0.492	-0.501
	(0.519)	(0.517)	(0.515)	(0.518)
Legal Wings	0.011	0.005	0.010	0.016
	(0.513)	(0.510)	(0.511)	(0.513)
Number of Rebel Groups	-0.136	-0.137	-0.142	-0.139
	(0.114)	(0.114)	(0.113)	(0.113)
Democracy	0.579	0.557	0.672	0.661
	(0.417)	(0.415)	(0.415)	(0.415)
Time (1 = Year of 1974)	0.074***	0.074***	0.078***	0.079***
	(0.020)	(0.020)	(0.020)	(0.020)
Time Since Last Commitment (t)	-0.097	-0.104	-0.103	-0.096
	(0.094)	(0.094)	(0.095)	(0.095)
t^2	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.000
	(0.007)	(0.007)	(0.007)	(0.007)
t^3	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)
Constant	-7.743***	-7.715***	-7.845***	-7.897***
	(1.278)	(1.271)	(1.288)	(1.294)
Var (Rebel Groups)	0.680	0.650	0.675	0.695
	(0.444)	(0.430)	(0.455)	(0.460)
Observations	1583	1583	1583	1583
AIC	487.42	487.35	488.68	488.88

Standard errors in parentheses *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

4.5.2 Civil Society Participation in Peace Negotiations

We investigated possible cases in which rebel groups were likely to be forced to make commitments to international law during the periods of peace negotiations. One of the possible sources to push rebel groups to commit to international law is civil society. As Nilsson (2005, 249-250) suggests, civil society participation in peace negotiations could lead warring parties to be more accountable for their actions and to behave in line with democratic values. In a similar vein, civil society actors such as human rights groups or international organizations may put pressures on the disputants to include humanitarian clauses in the peace agreements in order to reduce the risk of spoiler and keep more durable peace. Rebel groups are thus more likely to face strong demands for commitments to international law during peace negotiations with engagement of civil society organizations than otherwise. If this is the case and we find a number of cases with civil society involvement from our sample, the strong association between rebel commitment and peace negotiations may result from civil society's engagement in peace negotiations rather than rebel groups' willingness to signal their political viability and moderation.

To identify the cases in which civil society groups participated in peace negotiations, we use PA-X peace agreements data (PA-X 2017) that contain comprehensive information on peace agreements since 1990⁷ In particular, PA-X data provide information on participants (signatories) of peace agreements as well as a number of specific clauses. Using the information on participants of peace agreements, we find that, of 134 observations (rebel group \hat{A} year) that had any peace agreements between 1990 and 2010, only 12 observations are the cases with the involvement from civil society. This shows that it may not be prevalent for civil society organizations to participate in peace negotiations as signatories and put pressures on warring parties to abide by international law.

In addition, the engagement of civil society may not necessarily lead rebel groups to making more commitments. The results of t-tests and Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS) two-sample tests presented in Table A4-7 show that, during the periods of peace negotiations, the average number of rebel commitments for peace negotiations involving civil society is not different from it for those without civil society signatories.

Table A4-7: Average Number of Rebel Commitment during Peace Negotiations broken down by the Participation of Civil Society

Without civil society	With civil society	t-test	KS test
0.528	0.333	$p = 0.515$	$p = 0.990$

We further estimate logistic regression models of rebel commitments to examine whether the few cases with civil society participation may drive our main results of the strong association between peace negotiations and rebel commitment. Table A4-8 presents the results

⁷<https://www.peaceagreements.org/> University of Edinburgh, PA-X homepage. Bell, C. and Badanjak, S. (2019) 'Introducing PA-X: A new peace agreement database and dataset', *Journal of Peace Research*, 56 (3).

consistent with the conclusions we draw from the descriptive statistics mentioned above. In the first model (Model 1), we examine whether peace negotiations without civil society engagement can still promote rebel commitments. More specifically, Model 1 estimates the likelihood of rebel commitment using the sample excluding the observations for which civil society engaged in peace negotiations. If our finding of the association between peace talks and rebel commitment is driven by a few cases in which civil society engaged in peace negotiations, we should find statistically insignificant coefficient on *Near Peace Talks* in the Model 1. As presented in the first column of Table A4-8, however, the estimated coefficient on *Near Peace Talks* is positive and statistically significant at the 99% level, indicating that peace negotiations without strong involvement from civil society can also encourage rebel commitment.

In the second model (Model 2), we examine whether civil society participation makes a difference in the likelihood of rebel commitments, controlling for peace negotiations. In line with the results from Table A4-8, the positive but statistically insignificant coefficient on *Civil Society Participation* shows that civil society actors' engagement in peace negotiations does not necessarily lead rebel groups to make more commitments to international law. While civil society groups can urge warring parties to abide by international norms, their efforts might focus more on including humanitarian clauses in peace agreements rather than pushing disputants to make additional commitments.

In light of this empirical evidence, we find little support for the notion that rebel groups were "forced" to issue commitment documents.

Table A4-8: Effects of Civil Society Participation (Random Effects Logistic Regression Models)

	Model 1	Model 2
Civil Society Participation		1.345 (1.138)
Near Peace Talks	2.163*** (0.348)	2.209*** (0.350)
Non-military Transnational Support	0.889* (0.456)	0.903* (0.462)
Central Control Strength	0.715** (0.280)	0.673** (0.280)
Military Strength	0.747** (0.294)	0.783*** (0.296)
Territorial Control	0.931** (0.396)	0.938** (0.400)
Military Transnational Support	-0.236 (0.483)	-0.183 (0.487)
Secessionist	-0.099 (0.498)	-0.094 (0.502)
Age of Rebel Group	0.094*** (0.023)	0.094*** (0.023)
Extraterritorial Bases	0.859* (0.498)	0.813 (0.503)
Support by Foreign Government		
Non-military	-1.898** (0.909)	-1.872** (0.908)
Military	0.010 (0.400)	-0.033 (0.405)
Political Wings		
Unauthorized Wings	-0.786 (0.640)	-0.831 (0.642)
Legal Wings	-0.097 (0.515)	-0.083 (0.520)
Number of Rebel Groups	-0.040 (0.122)	-0.038 (0.123)
Democracy	-0.182 (0.456)	-0.170 (0.458)
Time (1 = Year of 1974)	0.107*** (0.030)	0.107*** (0.030)
Time Since Last Commitment (t)	0.056 (0.098)	0.060 (0.098)
t^2	-0.012 (0.008)	-0.012 (0.008)
t^3	0.000* (0.000)	0.000* (0.000)
Constant	-9.611*** (1.585)	-9.606*** (1.596)
Var (Rebel Groups)	0.692 (0.403)	0.742 (0.420)
Observations	969	976
AIC	474.64	482.60

Standard errors in parentheses *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

5 Model Performance

How well did our logistic regression models fit the data? To see this, we plotted the observed data against the predicted probabilities, as recommended by Greenhill et al. (2011). This avoids using an arbitrary threshold for prediction success and offers a concise visual summary of model performance. In the separation plots, the predicted probabilities are arranged from smallest to largest values on the horizontal axis, and dark colored lines mark observed commitments. The black line summarizes the value of the predicted probabilities. Better-fitting models have the observed values of one clustered to the right.

Figure A5-1: Separation Plots of Logistic Regression Models.

Figure A5-1 compares the predictive performance of the pooled logit model to the random effects logit model. The random effects model consistently assigns larger probabilities to observed commitments than the pooled logit model. More observed values are clustered on the right hand side of the x-axis in the random effects separation plot. Therefore, we use the random effects models to calculate substantive effects.

6 Text Analysis

Here, we report the results of a text analysis of rebel commitments: some word clouds to illustrate the document contents, as well as some topic models to show the text data patterns. We also present evidence from the LTTE to illustrate text data from the TheirWords archive.

Text analysis is the process of converting text data into inferences about the data generating process behind the text. Our goal is to understand the contents of rebel group commitment based on the lexical analysis, examining word frequency distributions, pattern recognition, association analysis, and visualization - not necessarily to test our hypotheses.

6.1 Word clouds

We first construct a word cloud to visualize the text data. To be clear, this word cloud is not a test of our theory, but it illustrates that rebel groups adopt their words to meet the expectation of their key audiences, by using certain themes, words, and languages of international humanitarian law that can resonate with international audiences.

The word cloud of the TheirWords corpus in Figure A6-1 shows the word types and frequencies in the data. This is for all years, 1928-2014 in TheirWords database and we treat each document as a bag of words.

“Forc,” “nation,” and “govern” are most frequent stem-words, the basic word form that produces various related words. So, “govern” could form various words like “governance,” “government,” or just the verb “govern.” There are also words related to international humanitarian law, such as “humanitarian,” “respect,” “children,” and “women” in these documents. From the word cloud, we observe that the primacy of political order and authority, as well as a role for international norms, in rebel groups’ vocabulary.

To begin, we collected each rebel commitment document from TheirWords directory. Text analysis requires plain text documents for the most valid inferences, so we hand-coded each (usually .pdf) document to plain text. We used Python to assist in basic file architecture, arranging documents by continent, year, and collapsing them all together. The corpus of text data features about 550 documents produced by about 60 rebel groups. Each word cloud is a visual representation of the abbreviated forms of the words in each document. In generating the data, we follow standard text analysis procedures: 1) the punctuation from each document is removed, 2) the so-called “stop words” (conjunctions, impersonal pronouns, articles, etc.) are removed, and 3) we “stem” the words to their most base form (Grimmer and Stewart 2013). Specifically, we collapse all rebel commitment documents, contained within each year, into a single Corpus, using the R package *tm* (Feinerer, Hornik, and Meyer 2008). The data are further transformed into a Document-Term-Matrix, the basic structure of text as data. We then use the R package *Wordcloud* to generate a word cloud of the frequency of the word stems within each year. For a word to appear in the word

6.2 Topic Models

Topic models are non-parametric computing methods to uncover the cluster of topics in the big data texts (Blei 2012). In the most basic topic model, the documents themselves have a most probable “topic” associated with them - where the topic has a latent dimension not directly observed by the analyst. The words within the documents and their associations across documents are empirical signals of the latent topics contained within the corpus of text data. For us, a topic model is useful because it uncovers the “topic” that generates each of the rebel commitments to international law. Further, because words are empirical signals of topics, the model helps us identify which words are the most commonly associated with the individual “topics” across the documents. Accordingly, we fit a five-topic model (suggested by model fit criteria) to the corpus of rebel commitments.

We also use topic models to uncover the topic that undergirds rebel commitment to international law. We report the five topics, their most common words, and the number of documents with each individual topic as its most probable subject in Table A6-1. The number assigned to each topic [Topic 1, Topic 2, etc.] is unrelated to its importance in the corpus.

Table A6-1: Five Topics from Rebels’ Words

	Most frequent stem-words appearing	Number of documents	Emerging topic
Topic 1	“nation” “govern” “parti” “transit” “polit” “law” “constitut”	32	Political demands
Topic 2	“parti” “agreement” “forc” “military”	79	War-related
Topic 3	“republ” “peac” “secur”	23	Peace-related
Topic 4	“group” “act” “dan” “sur”	18	Extras
Topic 5	“right” “children” “people” “human” “will”	114	International humanitarian norms

Note: A topic model fit to *TheirWords* with five topics.

Each topic is illustrated with its most frequent words.

Several clear themes emerge in Topic 1 and Topic 5. The theme of Topic 1 is related to political demands and institutions, such as nation, govern, and law; and the theme of Topic 5 is related to international humanitarian law (IHL) or related to human rights, containing such words like human, right, and children.⁸ Topic 2 contains many war-related words, such as force and military, while Topic 3 includes peace-related words such as peace and security. Topic 4 is the rest of the words, mostly articles. We also see the largest number of documents, 114 of them, mention IHL-related words. The topic model brings us the IHL-related topic regardless of the number of topics considered by the topic model.

⁸IHL and human rights are different research fields but they are increasingly blended together in the context of civil conflicts. See Alston and Goodman (2012).

Additionally, we plotted the topics for some rebel groups. Figure A6-2 features the topics of the Liberation Tigers of Tamil Eelam (LTTE, “Tamil Tigers”). We see that commitments near peace talks - 1995 and 2006 - were dominated by the topics related to international humanitarian law.⁹ This suggests a plausible links between rebel commitment and peace talks.

Figure A6-2: Tamil Tigers' Words.

⁹See Weiss (2012) for the history of Sri Lankan civil war.

6.3 Examples of Contents and Contexts

In 1977, at the height of its resistance against the South African government, the African National Congress wrote: “The President of the African National Council (ANC) informed the ICRC [International Committee of the Red Cross] that his movement would observe the Geneva Conventions and Protocols.”¹⁰ In 1998, after taking over the Afghan government in 1996, the Taliban issued a statement about anti-personnel mines: “The IEA [Islamic Emirate of Afghanistan] strongly condemns the production, trade, stockpiling and use of landmines, and considers it an un-Islamic and anti-human act.”¹¹ In 2002, the Moro Islamic Liberation Front (MILF) condemned the government of the Philippines by mentioning “... the Fourth Geneva Conventions were adopted by the community of nations on August 12, 1949, and Islam had already prescribed that non-combatants such as children, women, old people, monks or priests and the like are not the objects of war.”¹² In 2010, the Justice and Equality of Movement (JEM) of Darfur, Sudan called for “immediate and periodic reviews of JEM directives relating to observation of human rights and rights of children and their harmonization with relevant international conventions and ethos” during the establishment of a JEM committee for human rights.¹³

The striking commonality in these instances of rebel commitment is the interaction between rebel groups and international actors. The ANC deposited its commitment at the International Committee of the Red Cross; the Taliban made its commitment to ban anti-personnel mines thanking “all those countries that have signed the Ottawa treaty.”¹⁴ MILF, having rejected the peace deal in 1996, breaking away from the main faction, MNLF, retained its relations with transnational actors, becoming active on the humanitarian issues. The MILF’s central committee signed the Geneva Call’s deed of commitment in 2000 to handle landmine issue, and the United Nations which resulted in 2009 UN action plans to address the issue of child soldiers. JEM in Darfur, for its part, signed a Memorandum of Understanding with the UNICEF in the same year (2010).¹⁵ In a previous year, the rebel leadership committed itself to the protection of aid workers in the meeting with the Center for Humanitarian Dialogue.¹⁶ Interestingly, it was the time when the International Criminal Court issued the warrant to the Sudanese President Al-Bashir and when the attacks on humanitarian workers were rising. All these instances show that the rebel groups’ demand and appetite for international law is not enough to understand the making of soft law, but the interaction with international actors is the key ingredient to the production of soft law commitment.

¹⁰“Declarations of Adherence to the Geneva Conventions of 1949 and Additional Protocols I and II of 1977” (African National Congress 1997).

¹¹“Statement of the Islamic Emirate of Afghanistan on the Problem of Landmines” (Taliban 1998).

¹²“Resolution condemning Kidnapping” (MILF 2002).

¹³“Establishment of a JEM Committee for Human Rights” (JEM 2010).

¹⁴The clause also in the above cited Taliban statement.

¹⁵Memorandum of Understanding between the Justice and Equality Movement (JEM) and the United Nations regarding Protection of Children in Darfur. (2010).

¹⁶Sudan Tribune. “Darfur JEM says committed to supporting and protecting humanitarian work” 3 October 2009. <http://www.sudantribune.com/spip.php?article32656>

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